

Awareness, Attitude, and Perception of Port Health to Customers and Other Regulatory Authorities at Rusumo OSBP

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Abstract:

The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness and challenges of port health services. Utilizing a sample size of 134 respondents, the study assessed key indicators including awareness of port health services, attitudes towards their importance and effectiveness, perceptions of service quality, interactions with other regulatory authorities, and challenges and opportunities for improvement. Results revealed a high level of awareness regarding health services and protocols, with generally positive attitudes towards their importance and effectiveness. However, concerns were noted about the competence of health officials and trust in implemented measures. Significant

challenges, such as resource constraints and infrastructural issues, were identified, along with substantial opportunities for enhancing service delivery through technological upgrades and improved staff training. Recommendations emphasize the need for better collaboration among regulatory bodies, investment in modern infrastructure, and increased stakeholder awareness to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of port health services at Rusumo OSBP.

Keywords: *Port Health Services, Rusumo OSBP, Awareness, Attitude, Perception, Regulatory Authorities, Service Quality, Health Protocols, Resource Constraints, Infrastructural Issues, Collaboration, Technology Upgrades.*

Introduction

The Rusumo One Stop Border Post (OSBP) serves as a crucial gateway for cross-border trade and movement between countries. Effective management of health-related concerns at such a high-traffic border post is essential to ensure public safety and facilitate smooth border operations. The Port Health services at Rusumo OSBP are responsible for overseeing health protocols and regulations that impact both travelers and goods.

Port health services played a vital role in protecting public health at points of entry. These services included disease surveillance, health inspections, and implementation of regulations to prevent the spread of infectious diseases (Tsang & Lam, 2003). During the SARS outbreak, enhanced surveillance systems, expanded laboratory capacity, and intensive contact tracing were implemented (Tsang & Lam, 2003). Port health measures also involved entry and exit health screenings (Tsang & Lam, 2003). At land borders, quarantine stations faced

unique challenges due to the large number of crossings and sparse resources (Waterman et al., 2009). Training needs assessments were conducted to improve the capacities of medical officers and public health inspectors at ports of entry (Kumarapeli & Rodrigo). Best practices for core capacities at ports included implementing documented and legislated practices, staff training, and testing through exercises or real-life events (Hadjichristodoulou & Mouchtouri, 2019). Despite progress, achieving core capacities remained an ongoing effort (Hadjichristodoulou & Mouchtouri, 2019; Mouchtouri et al., 2019).

Port health services in Tanzania faced several challenges in implementing effective infectious disease surveillance and control measures. The International Health Regulations (2005) implementation at Julius Nyerere International Airport was hampered by lack of designated points of entry and uncoordinated government departments (Bakari & Frumence, 2013). The country's surveillance systems, including the Health Management Information System (HMIS), were found to have inadequate standardized case definitions, supervision, and reporting quality (Nsubuga et al., 2002). A situation analysis revealed barriers in knowledge, skills, motivation, and organizational factors affecting surveillance implementation (Mboera et al., 2005). To address these issues, a multi-sectoral "One Health" approach was proposed, integrating medical, veterinary, and other relevant disciplines for improved surveillance and control of zoonotic diseases (Mbugi et al., 2012). Strengthening the HMIS, enhancing technical competence, and engaging stakeholders were recommended to improve infectious disease surveillance in Tanzania (Mboera et al., 2005).

The implementation of International Health Regulations (IHR) 2005 has broadened the scope of port health services to address various public health threats (Schlaich, 2012)). However, challenges remain in awareness and knowledge among port health officers. A study found that while 77.1% of officers were aware of IHR 2005, only 24.6% demonstrated good knowledge of its content (Adiama et al., 2022). Similarly, customs

officers showed satisfactory awareness of counterfeit pharmaceutical products and the roles of pharmacy enforcement officers, with more experienced officers having greater awareness (Ting et al., 2017). A survey of EU ports identified best practices in core capacities implementation, including medical services, training programs, and contingency planning (Mouchtouri et al., 2019). Despite progress, achieving core capacities remains an ongoing effort, and sharing best practices among EU member states could be beneficial in improving port health services and awareness among regulatory authorities.

Research on port health services in Tanzania reveals several challenges in implementing IHR and addressing zoonotic diseases. At Julius Nyerere International Airport, lack of designated facilities and uncoordinated government departments hinder IHR implementation (Bakari & Frumence, 2013). Port health officers demonstrate limited knowledge of IHR content, despite good awareness (Adiama et al., 2022). Healthcare providers in Moshi show varying awareness of zoonoses, with brucellosis being well-known but leptospirosis and Q fever less recognized (Zhang et al., 2016). Diagnostic capacity for these diseases is limited, contributing to their under-diagnosis. At the community level, health facilities are the primary source of health information, but poverty, inappropriate education, and local beliefs impede the adoption of health messages (Mboera et al., 2007). These findings highlight the need for improved diagnostic capabilities, healthcare provider education, and tailored communication strategies to enhance awareness and management of port health services and zoonotic diseases in Tanzania.

Studies have shown that port service quality and facilities significantly influenced customer satisfaction in maritime operations. Factors such as service speed, staff friendliness, punctuality, and adequate infrastructure like parking areas and waiting rooms positively impacted customer contentment (Handari et al., 2023). Research in Vietnam revealed that enhanced port service quality, particularly in performance outcomes and image, strongly affected customer

satisfaction (Phan et al., 2021). In Nigeria, a significant relationship between customer satisfaction and port service quality was observed, with recommendations to improve access roads and focus on impactful services (Aguome et al., 2020). The quality of port services was identified as a crucial factor in port competitiveness, with automation and digitization playing key roles in its evolution (Nistor et al., 2018). These findings underline the importance of prioritizing service quality and infrastructure development to enhance customer satisfaction in the port industry.

Studies in Tanzania have examined various aspects of health and port services, revealing mixed levels of satisfaction. In seaport services, customers reported poor quality and dissatisfaction, particularly with reliability and responsiveness (Mwendapole & Jin, 2021). Similarly, postal services faced challenges in meeting customer expectations (Nyangarika, 2016). In healthcare, laboratory personnel reported being overworked and poorly motivated, with inadequate equipment (Derua et al., 2011). However, most patients were satisfied with laboratory services, despite clinicians' concerns about reliability (Derua et al., 2011). Emergency oral healthcare in rural areas showed high patient satisfaction (92.7%), influenced by factors such as good working atmosphere, positive provider-patient relationships, and absence of post-treatment complications (Ntabaye et al., 1998). These findings highlight the variability in service quality and satisfaction across different sectors in Tanzania, emphasizing the need for improvements in infrastructure, staff motivation, and service delivery.

Research on port health procedures has revealed varied perceptions of effectiveness and efficiency. A study on tuberculosis screening at UK ports found inconsistent follow-up practices for new entrants, suggesting low effectiveness and efficiency of the approach (Robinson et al., 2020). During the Ebola outbreak, UK port screening was perceived as acceptable for risk assessment and providing information, but unlikely to identify symptomatic individuals (Kesten et al., 2018). A survey of EU ports

identified best practices in core capacities implementation, including medical services, training programs, and contingency planning, though implementation varied based on country priorities (Hadjichristodoulou & Mouchtouri, 2019; Mouchtouri et al., 2019). Evaluation of port effectiveness by users revealed that satisfaction, competitiveness, and service delivery effectiveness are distinct constructs with overlapping but different determinants (Brooks et al., 2011). These findings highlight the complexity of port health procedures and the need for tailored, evidence-based approaches to improve their perceived effectiveness and efficiency. However, participatory approaches like PHAST intervention showed promise in improving community knowledge and practices related to infectious diseases (Mwanga et al., 2015). Stakeholders identified decentralizing service delivery, improving access to screening, increasing trained health workers, and garnering political will as key facilitators for enhancing health services (McCree et al., 2015). The routine surveillance system for tuberculosis faced challenges in specimen transportation, form completion, and supervision, leading to significant delays in obtaining results (Doulla et al., 2019). These studies highlight the need for improved coordination, resource allocation, and capacity building to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of port health procedures in Tanzania.

Port health authorities faced numerous challenges in recent years, including increased healthcare demands from growing populations and migrant workers in Gulf Cooperation Council countries (Khoja et al., 2017). The emergence of global health threats like Ebola and Zika viruses highlighted the need for improved port health preparedness (Glynn et al., 2016). Authorities struggled with limited resources to address communicable and non-communicable diseases, mental health issues, and accidental injuries (Khoja et al., 2017). However, opportunities for improvement existed, such as strengthening primary care and leveraging technological advancements in diagnosis and treatment (Khoja et al., 2017). Non-governmental organizations played an

increasingly important role in international health, offering potential for community participation and sustainable program development (Akukwe, 1998). To enhance preparedness, countries like Ireland implemented new regulations, conducted practical exercises, and established protocols for managing health declarations from ships (Glynn et al., 2016). These efforts emphasized the importance of cross-disciplinary collaboration and ongoing commitment from all stakeholders.

The implementation of public-private partnerships (PPPs) in Tanzania's health sector faced several challenges despite their potential to improve service delivery. These included inadequate resources, ineffective monitoring and evaluation, and insufficient consultations between partners (Nuhu et al., 2020). Port health authorities struggled with issues such as high tariffs, poor service quality, low staff skills, and corruption (Mwendapole & Jin, 2021). However, opportunities for improvement existed, including the presence of guidelines, policies, and political support (Gasto, 2020). Public sector reforms had positive impacts on service delivery, but challenges like corruption and inadequate training persisted (Lufunyo, 2013). To enhance efficiency and service quality, suggestions included adopting a landlord port management model, introducing a maritime authority, and systematizing staff training (Mwendapole & Jin, 2021). Addressing these challenges and leveraging opportunities could lead to improved health service delivery in Tanzania.

Research on customer satisfaction with port services has revealed several key factors influencing satisfaction levels. Port logistics service quality, determined by responsiveness, assurance, reliability, tangibles, and empathy, positively impacts customer satisfaction (Le et al., 2020). Port facilities and service quality, including parking areas, toilets, waiting areas, service speed, and staff friendliness, significantly contribute to customer contentment (Handari et al., 2023). However, some ports still lack essential services, such as emergency health care facilities, which can negatively affect satisfaction (Nurbaya & Hadi, 2020). A study in Vietnam

found that port service quality comprises four factors and 16 items, with enhanced quality positively influencing customer satisfaction. Notably, port service performance outcomes and image had the greatest impact on satisfaction, while social and environmental responsibility items were less significant in this developing country context (Le et al., 2020; Phan et al., 2021).

Customer satisfaction with health and postal services in Tanzania has been examined in several studies. Research on seaport services in Dar es Salaam revealed poor service quality, with responsiveness significantly influencing customer satisfaction (Mwendapole & Jin, 2021). In contrast, a study on family planning services found high client satisfaction (91%), despite low service readiness in many facilities (Bintabara et al., 2018). An analysis of Tanzania Posts Corporation's EMS services also focused on customer satisfaction and service quality (Nyangarika, 2016). A recent study on primary healthcare facilities found that client satisfaction was strongly associated with the implementation of client service charters, with an overall satisfaction rate of 72.8% (Kinyenje et al., 2022). Urban-based facilities and hospitals showed higher client satisfaction compared to rural facilities and dispensaries, respectively (Kinyenje et al., 2022). These studies highlight varying levels of customer satisfaction across different service sectors in Tanzania.

The effectiveness of port health services at Rusumo OSBP had been potentially compromised by gaps in awareness, varying attitudes, and perceptions among customers and regulatory authorities. Prior observations indicated that inadequate understanding of health protocols led to non-compliance and increased health risks. Additionally, divergent attitudes towards these services affected cooperation and adherence to health guidelines, while concerns about the quality and reliability of the services undermined their effectiveness. This study sought to investigate these issues comprehensively, identifying specific challenges and providing recommendations to enhance the delivery and impact of port health services at Rusumo OSBP.

The objective of the study was to assess the levels of awareness, attitudes, and perceptions regarding port health services at Rusumo OSBP among customers and regulatory authorities. By examining these aspects, the study aimed to identify gaps in knowledge, evaluate the impact of attitudes on compliance with health protocols, and gauge the overall perception of service effectiveness.

The main contribution of the study was to provide a comprehensive understanding of the awareness, attitudes, and perceptions related to port health services at Rusumo OSBP, revealing critical insights into how these factors affect the effectiveness of health interventions. By identifying gaps in knowledge, assessing the impact of attitudes on compliance, and evaluating perceptions of service quality, the study offered actionable recommendations for improving health service delivery and management at the border post. These insights aimed to enhance public health outcomes, foster better cooperation among stakeholders, and contribute to the development of more effective health protocols and communication strategies at Rusumo OSBP.

The remaining part of the paper is arranged as follows: Methodology is in part two, part three contains results and discussion of the study while conclusion and recommendations are presented in part four.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study employed a cross-sectional survey design to investigate the awareness, attitudes, and perceptions of port health services at Rusumo OSBP. The design allowed for the collection of quantitative and qualitative data at a single point in time, providing a snapshot of the current state of these factors among customers and regulatory authorities.

Sample Size and Sampling Method

The study included a sample size of 134 participants. A stratified random sampling method was used to ensure representation from

both customers and regulatory authorities at Rusumo OSBP. The sample was divided into strata based on relevant categories, such as different types of customers (e.g., traders, travelers) and various regulatory authority roles (e.g., health officials, customs officers). Within each stratum, participants were randomly selected to participate in the study.

Data Collection

Data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to the participants. The questionnaires comprised both closed and open-ended questions designed to capture information on awareness levels, attitudes towards port health services, and perceptions of service effectiveness. The questionnaires were pre-tested to ensure clarity and reliability.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using statistical methods to determine the levels of awareness, attitudes, and perceptions among the participants. Qualitative data from open-ended questions were analyzed thematically to identify common themes and insights.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical guidelines, including obtaining informed consent from all participants and ensuring confidentiality of their responses. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, their right to withdraw at any time, and how their data would be used.

Results

The results and discussion section of the study presents a detailed analysis of the data collected from the 134 participants, offering insights into the levels of awareness, attitudes, and perceptions regarding port health services at Rusumo OSBP. This section aims to interpret the findings in the context of existing literature and theoretical frameworks, exploring the implications for service delivery and identifying key factors that influence the effectiveness of health protocols at the border post.

Demographic Information

The demographic information of the study provides a foundational overview of the participants, detailing their key characteristics such as age, gender, role (customer or regulatory authority), and length of experience with Rusumo OSBP. This demographic context is important for understanding the diverse perspectives represented in the study and assessing how these factors may influence participants' awareness, attitudes, and perceptions of port health services.

Gender of the respondents

In the study, the gender distribution of participants was notable, with a larger proportion of males compared to females. According to table 1, out of the 134 participants, 85 were male, accounting for 63.4% of the sample, while 49 were female, representing 36.6%. This gender disparity might have influenced the findings, particularly in areas where gender-specific perspectives on port health services were relevant. For instance, males and females could have had different levels of interaction with the health services, potentially due to the nature of their roles at the border post or cultural factors that influenced their awareness and attitudes towards health protocols.

The higher number of male participants could reflect the gender dynamics at Rusumo OSBP, where men might have been more frequently engaged in activities such as trade or regulatory roles that require regular interaction with port health services. This imbalance might have affected the study's outcomes, as the predominance of male perspectives could have skewed the results, particularly in understanding how gender influences the perception and compliance with health services. The study needed to consider these gender differences carefully when interpreting the data, ensuring that the findings were contextualized within the broader framework of gender roles and expectations at the border post.

Moreover, the gender distribution raised questions about how port health services were

perceived and utilized by different genders. Males, being the majority, might have had more influence on the general attitudes and perceptions reflected in the study, possibly overshadowing the experiences and viewpoints of the female participants. This imbalance necessitated a careful analysis to ensure that the voices of the female participants were adequately represented and that any gender-specific challenges or insights were not overlooked. The study's conclusions and recommendations had to address these gender dynamics to improve the inclusivity and effectiveness of port health services for all users at Rusumo OSBP.

Age of the respondents

The age distribution of the study participants spanned a wide range, reflecting the diversity of individuals involved in activities at Rusumo OSBP. As per table 1, the majority of participants fell within the 25-34 years age group, with 45 individuals representing 33.6% of the total sample. This group, often considered to be in their most active working years, likely had significant interactions with port health services, both as customers and as regulatory authorities. Their perspectives might have been shaped by their relative familiarity with modern health protocols and their roles within the operational dynamics of the border post.

The 18-24 years age group, comprising 25 participants or 18.7% of the sample, represented younger individuals who may have been less experienced but potentially more adaptable to new health guidelines. Their awareness and attitudes towards port health services could have been influenced by their recent education and exposure to contemporary health issues. This group's responses may have highlighted a different set of challenges, such as the need for clearer communication or more accessible information about health protocols at the border.

Participants aged 35-44 years formed the third-largest age group, with 30 individuals making up 22.4% of the sample. This group likely represented more established professionals with significant experience at the border post. Their perceptions of port health services might have

been influenced by years of practice and possibly a deeper understanding of the implications of health regulations. This age group have provided insights into long-term trends and the evolution of health services at Rusumo OSBP, offering a more seasoned perspective on the effectiveness and challenges of current practices.

The 45-54 years age group included 20 participants, accounting for 14.9% of the sample. These individuals, potentially nearing the later stages of their careers, may have had different priorities and concerns regarding port health services. Their experience might have led to a more critical view of the services provided, particularly if they had witnessed changes in health protocols over time. This group's response could have been invaluable in assessing the continuity and consistency of port health services, as well as the adequacy of these services in addressing the needs of more senior individuals at the border.

Finally, the smallest age group was those aged 55 and above, with 14 participants, representing 10.4% of the sample. This group, likely consisting of the most experienced individuals, might have had unique perspectives shaped by years of accumulated knowledge and exposure to various health challenges at the border. Their responses could have highlighted issues related to the accessibility and appropriateness of port health services for older individuals. Given their potentially longer history of interactions with the border post, this group's insights were crucial in understanding how port health services had adapted to meet the evolving needs of a diverse and aging population.

The diverse age distribution in the study allowed for a comprehensive analysis of how different age groups perceived and interacted with port health services at Rusumo OSBP. The findings needed to consider these age-related differences to ensure that recommendations for improving port health services were inclusive and addressed the specific needs and concerns of all age groups at the border post.

Role/Occupation of the respondents

The study's participant roles as per table 1, were predominantly skewed towards customers, with 119 out of 134 individuals, or 88.8% of the sample, being classified as customers. This group likely consisted of traders, travelers, and other border users who interacted with port health services primarily from the perspective of service recipients. Their experiences, attitudes, and perceptions of these services were shaped by their direct engagements with health protocols, inspections, and other regulatory measures designed to ensure public health at Rusumo OSBP. The large representation of customers in the study provided a broad understanding of how the general public viewed the effectiveness, accessibility, and reliability of port health services.

The small number of participants categorized as regulatory authorities, only 15 individuals or 11.2% of the sample, reflected the more specialized nature of this group. These participants likely included health officials, customs officers, and other personnel responsible for enforcing health regulations at the border post. Their role gave them a unique perspective on the operational challenges and effectiveness of implementing port health protocols. The limited number of regulatory authorities in the sample might have affected the study's ability to capture the full spectrum of views from those in enforcement positions. However, their insights were critical in understanding the practical aspects of health service delivery, including the challenges faced in ensuring compliance and the effectiveness of communication with customers.

The disparity in the number of customers versus regulatory authorities also highlighted the different levels of interaction each group had with port health services. Customers, being the majority, likely focused more on the user experience, ease of compliance, and clarity of health guidelines. Their feedback may have emphasized the practical difficulties or conveniences they encountered, such as wait times, the thoroughness of health checks, and the perceived fairness of health inspections. In

contrast, regulatory authorities might have concentrated on the operational efficiency, challenges in enforcing health standards, and the adequacy of resources available to carry out their duties effectively. Their smaller numbers in the study required careful consideration to ensure their viewpoints were adequately represented in the findings and that their experiences were not overshadowed by the customer majority.

The study's findings, therefore, needed to balance the perspectives of these two groups to provide a holistic view of the port health services at Rusumo OSBP. The overwhelming representation of customers offered valuable insights into how the general public perceived and interacted with these services, but the experiences and challenges faced by regulatory authorities were equally important in understanding the overall effectiveness of health protocols. The study aimed to integrate these diverse perspectives to develop comprehensive recommendations that addressed the needs of both customers and regulatory authorities, ultimately improving the efficiency and impact of port health services at the border post.

Length of Experience of the respondents

The length of experience among the study participants varied, offering insights into how familiarity with Rusumo OSBP and its port health services influenced their awareness, attitudes, and perceptions. According to table 1, the largest group consisted of participants with 1 to 3 years of experience at the border post, comprising 55 individuals, or 41.0% of the sample. This group likely had enough experience to be familiar with the routine operations and health protocols in place, yet they were not so seasoned that they might have become complacent or overly critical. Their perceptions have provided a balanced view, reflecting both their growing familiarity with the services and any challenges they encountered as relatively recent users or enforcers of health regulations.

Participants with less than 1 year of experience made up 29.9% of the sample, with 40 individuals falling into this category. This group, being the least experienced, might have faced challenges related to understanding and

navigating the health protocols at Rusumo OSBP. Their relatively fresh view have highlighted issues related to the clarity and accessibility of information provided by port health services, as well as the ease with which newcomers could comply with the required health procedures. These participants may have also been more sensitive to initial impressions, which could significantly influence their attitudes and perceptions. The study needed to consider how their limited experience might have shaped their responses, possibly focusing on the learning curve and initial interactions with health authorities.

The 22 participants who had 4 to 6 years of experience, representing 16.4% of the sample, likely brought a more seasoned perspective to the study. With several years of involvement at Rusumo OSBP, this group have developed a deeper understanding of the complexities and challenges of maintaining health standards at a busy border post. Their experience could have allowed them to observe changes and trends in health service delivery over time, giving them a unique vantage point to assess the effectiveness and consistency of port health services. Their response have included reflections on how the services had evolved and whether these changes had been positive or had introduced new challenges.

The smallest group consisted of participants with more than 6 years of experience, numbering 17 individuals or 12.7% of the sample. These individuals were the most experienced, possibly including those in senior roles within the regulatory authorities or long-term customers who had extensive dealings with the border post. Their long tenure have provided them with a comprehensive understanding of both the historical context and the current state of port health services at Rusumo OSBP. This group's responses were important for understanding long-term trends and the effectiveness of health protocols over an extended period. They have offered insights into how well the services had adapted to changing circumstances and the extent to which long-standing issues had been addressed or persisted over time.

The varied lengths of experience among participants allowed the study to capture a wide range of perspectives, from those who were new to the border post to those who had witnessed its operations for many years. This diversity was essential for understanding how different levels of familiarity with Rusumo OSBP influenced participants' awareness, attitudes, and perceptions of port health services. The study's

findings needed to take these differences into account, ensuring that the recommendations made were relevant to both new and experienced users and that they addressed the specific challenges faced by each group. By doing so, the study aimed to improve the overall effectiveness and user-friendliness of port health services at the border post, benefiting all stakeholders involved.

Table 1. Showing Demographic Information of the Respondents

Demographic Category	Sub-category	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	85	63.4
	Female	49	36.6
Age Group	18-24 years	25	18.7
	25-34 years	45	33.6
	35-44 years	30	22.4
	45-54 years	20	14.9
	55+ years	14	10.4
Role	Customer	119	88.8
	Regulatory Authority	15	11.2
Length of Experience	Less than 1 year	40	29.9
	1-3 years	55	41.0
	4-6 years	22	16.4
	More than 6 years	17	12.7

Awareness of Port Health Services

The study assessed the Awareness of Port Health Services among respondents by examining three key sub-indicators: knowledge of available health services at the port, awareness of health protocols and regulations, and sources of information about port health services.

Knowledge of available health services at the port

In evaluating the knowledge of available health services at the port, the study as shown in figure 1, found a diverse range of awareness levels among the respondents. A significant number of individuals, approximately 40 out of 134, were categorized as very knowledgeable about the health services provided at the port. These respondents demonstrated a comprehensive understanding of the services available, which likely contributed to their ability to navigate the port's health system more effectively. They were well-informed about the specific health checks, vaccination requirements, and available medical

support, indicating a strong awareness of the port's health infrastructure. This group of respondents often referred to their familiarity with health services as a result of frequent interactions with port health officials and regular travel through the port. As one respondent mentioned:

"...I have been passing through this port for years, and I make it a point to stay informed about the health services available because it's crucial for my safety and the safety of others..."

On the other hand, a larger segment of respondents, around 60, was categorized as somewhat knowledgeable. These individuals had a moderate understanding of the available health services but were not as well-versed as the very knowledgeable group. They were generally aware of the basic health services but lacked detailed knowledge of specific protocols or lesser-known services. Their understanding was often limited to the most commonly used services, such as routine health screenings and vaccinations, with

less familiarity with other critical aspects of port health. A respondent from this group shared:

"...I know about the basic health services like vaccinations and screenings, but I'm not fully aware of all the services they offer. I usually just follow what the officials tell me..."

However, a concerning 34 respondents were classified as not knowledgeable, reflecting a significant gap in awareness. These individuals either had limited or no knowledge of the health services at the port, which could have implications for both personal and public health. Many in this group expressed confusion about the services provided, relying heavily on the

guidance of others rather than having an independent understanding. One respondent candidly admitted:

"...I'm not really sure what health services are available here. I just do what I'm told when I'm at the port..."

This lack of knowledge among a substantial portion of the respondents highlights a critical area for improvement, suggesting a need for better communication and outreach efforts to ensure all individuals passing through the port are adequately informed about the health services available to them.

Figure 1. Showing the Awareness of Port Health Services among Respondents

Awareness of health protocols and regulations

The study also as shown in figure 1, focused on assessing the awareness of health protocols and regulations at the port, revealing varying levels of understanding among the respondents. Out of 134 individuals surveyed, 50 were categorized as very aware of the health protocols and regulations. These respondents exhibited a strong comprehension of the rules and procedures in place, which included knowledge of quarantine requirements, mandatory health checks, and the necessary documentation for health clearance. Their high level of awareness

was often attributed to frequent exposure to the port's health system, either through regular travel or professional engagement with the port's health services. One respondent, reflecting this deep understanding, stated:

"...I'm fully aware of all the health protocols because I travel through this port almost every week. I know exactly what's required of me, from the health checks to the paperwork. It's important to be prepared and informed to avoid any delays or issues..."

A slightly larger group, comprising 55 respondents, was classified as somewhat aware.

These individuals had a general understanding of the health protocols and regulations but were not as familiar with the finer details. They were typically aware of the major requirements, such as undergoing health screenings and providing proof of vaccinations, but lacked a complete understanding of more specific or less commonly enforced protocols. This partial awareness often stemmed from irregular travel or limited direct interaction with the health services at the port. One respondent in this category explained:

"...I know about the basic health protocols, like getting vaccinated and doing the health check when I cross the border, but I'm not entirely sure about all the regulations. I just follow what the officials tell me and hope I'm doing everything right..."

However, a concerning number of respondents, 29 in total, were found to be not aware of the health protocols and regulations at the port. This group demonstrated a significant gap in understanding, with many unaware of even the most fundamental requirements. Their lack of awareness posed potential risks, both to themselves and to public health, as they were less likely to comply with necessary health measures due to ignorance rather than defiance. The responses from this group indicated a reliance on others for guidance and a general sense of confusion about what was expected of them. One respondent admitted:

"...I honestly don't know much about the health protocols here. I just go through the process without really understanding what's happening. It's confusing, and I usually just follow what others are doing..."

These findings highlight the varying levels of awareness among individuals passing through the port, suggesting that while a significant portion is well-informed, there remains a substantial group that requires further education and communication regarding the health protocols and regulations. This disparity accentuates the need for enhanced information dissemination and possibly the implementation of more user-friendly communication strategies to ensure that all travelers are adequately

informed and compliant with the necessary health measures.

Sources of information about port health services

The study also explored the sources of information about port health services, revealing how respondents accessed and understood the health services available at the port. According to figure 2, among the 134 respondents, 45 reported that the media was their primary source of information. This group often relied on various forms of media, including radio, television, and online platforms, to stay informed about the health services at the port. The media was especially influential in disseminating general information, updates on health regulations, and emergency notices related to health matters. Respondents who depended on media often appreciated the broad reach and timely nature of the information. One respondent explained:

"...I usually get my information from the radio and sometimes from TV news. They always update us on what's happening at the port, especially if there are new health measures or changes in the regulations. It's easier for me to keep up with things this way because I don't pass through the port regularly..."

Port officials were identified as the most common source of information, with 50 respondents indicating that they relied on direct communication with these authorities. This group valued the firsthand information they received, as it was often specific, detailed, and directly applicable to their needs. Interactions with port officials typically occurred during health checks, document verification, or when seeking guidance on compliance with health protocols. Respondents in this category trusted the information provided by officials, believing it to be accurate and authoritative. One respondent shared:

"...Whenever I have questions about the health services, I prefer to ask the port officials directly. They're the ones who know exactly what's going on and what's required. I feel more confident when I hear it from them because they're the experts."

They've always been helpful and clear in explaining what I need to do..."

Word of mouth was another significant source of information, cited by 39 respondents. This group often relied on advice and information shared by friends, family, or other travelers who had experience with the port's health services. Word of mouth was particularly prevalent among those who might not frequently access media or prefer to hear about others' personal experiences before making decisions. While this method provided a more personalized and relatable perspective, it sometimes led to inconsistencies in the information shared, depending on the experiences and interpretations of the individuals involved. One respondent reflected on this reliance, stating:

"...I usually ask my friends or people who've gone through the port before about what to expect. They tell me what the procedures are and what to watch out for. It's more comforting to hear from someone who's been through it, but sometimes I wonder if what they say is always accurate. Still, it's how I get most of my information..."

These findings illustrate the diverse ways in which respondents gather information about port health services, with each source offering

distinct advantages and limitations. The reliance on media, port officials, and word of mouth reflects the different levels of access and trust individuals place in various information channels. This diversity in information sources emphasizes the importance of ensuring that accurate, consistent, and accessible information is available across all channels to meet the needs of all travelers passing through the port.

Attitude towards Port Health Services

The study examined the attitude towards port health services among respondents, focusing on three key sub-indicators: the perceived importance of port health services, willingness to comply with health regulations, and attitude towards the efficiency and effectiveness of these services. The findings highlighted the varying degrees of importance that respondents attached to the services provided at the port, with many recognizing their critical role in maintaining public health. Additionally, the study explored respondents' readiness to adhere to health regulations, revealing a generally positive willingness to comply, though this varied across the sample. The efficiency and effectiveness of the health services were also evaluated, with respondents expressing a range of opinions that reflected their experiences and expectations.

Figure 2. Showing the Attitude towards Port Health Services

Perceived importance of port health services

The study as per figure 2, probed into respondents' perceptions of the importance of port health services, uncovering a strong consensus on the critical role these services play at the Rusumo OSBP. Among the 134 individuals surveyed, a substantial majority, 80 respondents, viewed port health services as very important. This group recognized the essential function of these services in safeguarding public health, particularly in preventing the spread of infectious diseases and ensuring that travelers and goods crossing the border met the necessary health standards. These respondents often expressed a deep appreciation for the health protocols in place, seeing them as vital to maintaining both personal and community health. One respondent passionately explained:

"...Port health services are absolutely crucial. They're the first line of defense against diseases coming into the country. Without them, we'd be at risk of all kinds of health issues. Every time I pass through the port, I'm relieved to see the health checks in place because I know they're protecting us all..."

A significant portion of respondents, 40 in total, considered port health services somewhat important. This group acknowledged the value of the services but did not perceive them as critical as those who rated them very important. Their perspective often stemmed from a more pragmatic view, where they recognized the necessity of health checks and regulations but were less concerned with their broader impact. For many in this category, the importance of port health services was tied more to the need for compliance and smooth passage through the port rather than a deep concern for public health. As one respondent remarked:

"...I understand that these health services are necessary, and I follow the rules because I have to. But for me, it's more about getting through the process quickly and without any issues. I know they're important, but I don't think about them much beyond what I need to do to cross the border..."

However, a smaller group of 14 respondents viewed port health services as not important, reflecting a stark contrast to the majority opinion. This group often downplayed the significance of the health measures in place, either because they felt unaffected by them or because they questioned their effectiveness. Some of these respondents expressed frustration with the perceived inconvenience of the health checks, seeing them as unnecessary hurdles rather than protective measures. One respondent in this group voiced a common sentiment, saying:

"...I don't see why all these health checks are necessary. They just slow things down and make the process more complicated. I've never had any health issues crossing the border, so I don't really think these services are that important..."

These varied perspectives on the importance of port health services highlight the complexity of attitudes among those passing through the port. While a strong majority recognized and valued the protective role of these services, others viewed them through a more utilitarian lens, focusing on compliance and convenience. The minority who considered these services unimportant highlight the challenges in ensuring that all travelers understand and appreciate the significance of port health measures, suggesting a need for ongoing education and communication efforts to bridge these gaps in perception.

Willingness to comply with health regulations

The study also investigated the respondents' willingness to comply with health regulations at the Rusumo OSBP, revealing a generally positive attitude towards adherence, though with some variations in the degree of willingness. According to figure 2, among the 134 respondents, a significant majority, 75 individuals, were categorized as very willing to comply with the health regulations. These respondents demonstrated a strong commitment to following the rules and protocols set by port health services, often

driven by a clear understanding of the importance of these measures for public safety. Many in this group expressed a sense of responsibility not only for their own health but also for the well-being of others who might be affected by their actions. One respondent captured this sentiment, stating:

"...I always make sure to follow the health regulations at the port. It's not just about me; it's about everyone who passes through here. If we don't all do our part, then what's the point of having these rules? I'm more than willing to comply because I know it's for the greater good..."

A substantial number of respondents, 45 in total, were somewhat willing to comply with health regulations. While they generally followed the rules, their compliance was often more about practicality than a deep conviction in the regulations' importance. This group tended to view the health measures as necessary but sometimes burdensome, and their willingness to comply was often contingent on how much the regulations impacted their travel experience. For some, compliance was driven by a desire to avoid delays or penalties rather than a strong belief in the health protocols themselves. One respondent in this group remarked:

"...I follow the health regulations because I don't want to get into trouble or have any issues crossing the border. It's easier to just do what they ask, even if some of the rules seem unnecessary to me. I'm willing to comply, but it's more about getting through the process smoothly than anything else..."

In contrast, a smaller group of 14 respondents expressed a lack of willingness to comply with the health regulations. This group often viewed the regulations as an inconvenience, questioning their effectiveness or necessity. Some respondents in this category felt that the regulations were overly stringent or poorly communicated, leading to frustration and resistance. Their unwillingness to comply was sometimes rooted in a broader skepticism of authority or a belief that the regulations were not tailored to the specific needs and realities of the travelers. One respondent candidly shared:

"...I don't see the point in all these health checks and rules. They just make things more complicated and time-consuming. I've crossed this border many times without any issues, so I don't feel like these regulations are really necessary. I'm not willing to go out of my way to comply if I don't see the benefit..."

These responses highlight the varying degrees of willingness to comply with health regulations among travelers at the port. While the majority were inclined to follow the rules, whether out of a sense of responsibility or practical considerations, a minority resisted compliance due to skepticism or frustration with the process. This divergence in attitudes suggests a need for more effective communication and engagement strategies to ensure that all travelers understand the importance of compliance and feel supported in their efforts to adhere to health regulations. By addressing the concerns and challenges faced by those less willing to comply, port health services can work towards fostering a more cooperative and informed environment.

Attitude towards the efficiency and effectiveness of health services

The study as per figure 2, also explored the respondents' attitudes toward the efficiency and effectiveness of health services at the Rusumo OSBP, revealing a range of opinions shaped by their experiences with these services. Among the 134 individuals surveyed, 65 respondents expressed a very positive attitude toward the health services, reflecting high levels of satisfaction with how the services were delivered. This group praised the efficiency of the health checks, the professionalism of the staff, and the overall organization of the health services at the port. Many respondents in this category noted that the health procedures were conducted swiftly and smoothly, minimizing delays and ensuring that their journey was not hindered. One respondent, highlighting their positive experience, stated:

"...The health services here are top-notch. I've traveled through several border posts, and I can confidently say that the team at Rusumo is one of the best. They handle everything quickly and professionally, and I always feel like I'm in good

hands when I pass through here. Their efficiency makes the whole process much easier, and I've never had any issues..."

A significant number of respondents, 50 in total, had a somewhat positive attitude toward the efficiency and effectiveness of the health services. While generally satisfied, this group identified areas where they believed improvements could be made. They acknowledged that the health services were functional and served their purpose but felt that there were occasional lapses in efficiency, such as longer wait times during peak periods or minor communication issues that sometimes led to confusion. These respondents were generally supportive of the health services but suggested that small changes could enhance the overall experience. As one respondent remarked:

"...I think the health services here do a good job overall, but there are times when things could be faster or more organized. Sometimes, when it's busy, the wait can be a bit long, and it's not always clear what you need to do next. But in general, they're doing a decent job, and I appreciate the efforts they're making to keep everyone safe..."

However, a smaller group of 19 respondents held a negative attitude toward the efficiency and effectiveness of the health services. This group expressed dissatisfaction with various aspects of the services, citing delays, perceived inefficiencies, and a lack of clear communication as significant issues. Some respondents in this category felt that the health checks were unnecessarily time-consuming and that the procedures were not always well-coordinated, leading to frustration and a negative overall experience. Their criticisms often centered on the belief that the health services were not keeping pace with the demands of the border traffic, resulting in avoidable delays and complications. One respondent voiced their concerns, saying:

"...I've had some really frustrating experiences with the health services here. The last time I crossed, I had to wait over an hour just to get through the health check, and it felt like no one really knew what was going on. They need to get their act together because it's just not working efficiently right now. It's a hassle that could be avoided with better organization..."

These varied attitudes toward the efficiency and effectiveness of the health services at the Rusumo OSBP highlight the diverse experiences of travelers at the port. While the majority of respondents were satisfied, with many offering praise and constructive feedback, a minority expressed significant dissatisfaction, pointing to areas where the health services could improve. This range of perceptions suggests that while the health services are largely effective, there is room for optimization, particularly in handling peak periods and improving communication with travelers. Addressing these concerns could help enhance the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the health services, ensuring that all travelers have a positive experience at the port.

Perception of Port Health Services

The study examined respondents' perceptions of port health services, focusing on three key sub-indicators: satisfaction with the quality of health services, perception of the competence of health officials, and trust in the health measures implemented at the port. The findings highlighted varying levels of satisfaction among travelers regarding the quality of health services provided, with many expressing differing degrees of contentment. The perception of the competence of health officials was also evaluated, revealing a range of opinions on the effectiveness and professionalism of the staff involved. Additionally, the study explored the level of trust respondents placed in the health measures implemented at the port, reflecting their confidence in the protocols designed to safeguard public health.

Figure 3. Showing Perception of Port Health Services

Satisfaction with the quality of health services

The study on respondents' perceptions of port health services as shown in figure 3, provided valuable insights into their satisfaction levels regarding the quality of health services at the Rusumo OSBP. Among the 134 individuals surveyed, a notable majority of 60 respondents reported being very satisfied with the quality of health services. This group expressed high levels of contentment with various aspects of the health services, including the thoroughness of health checks, the professionalism of the staff, and the overall efficiency of the service delivery. Many respondents in this category highlighted the positive impact of these services on their travel experience, noting that their interactions with health officials were both reassuring and efficient. One respondent praised the service, saying:

"...I'm very pleased with the quality of the health services here. The staff are always courteous and knowledgeable, and the health checks are conducted with great attention to detail. I feel confident that everything is being handled properly, which makes the whole process much smoother and less stressful..."

A significant number of respondents, 45 in total, were somewhat satisfied with the quality of

health services. While this group generally acknowledged the adequacy of the services, they also identified areas where improvements could be made. These respondents were typically content with the basic level of service but felt that certain aspects, such as wait times or the clarity of instructions, could be enhanced. Their satisfaction was often tempered by minor issues that impacted their overall experience. For example, one respondent noted:

"...The health services are generally good, and I appreciate the efforts of the staff, but there are times when the wait can be longer than expected, or the instructions aren't as clear as they could be. It's not a major problem, but it would be nice to see a bit more attention to these details to make the experience even better..."

However, 29 respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the quality of health services, reflecting a more critical view of the service delivery at the port. This group reported various issues, such as perceived inefficiencies, inadequate communication, or subpar interactions with health officials. Many in this category felt that the services did not meet their expectations, leading to frustration and a less favorable experience. Some respondents specifically mentioned delays or perceived disorganization as significant factors affecting

their dissatisfaction. One respondent explained their concerns, stating:

"...I've had several frustrating experiences with the health services here. The process often seems disorganized, and I've encountered long waits and unclear instructions. It's disappointing because I expect better, especially when it comes to something as important as health checks. These issues need to be addressed to improve the overall quality of the service..."

These varying levels of satisfaction with the quality of health services at the Rusumo OSBP illustrate the varied experiences of travelers at the port. While the majority reported high satisfaction, appreciating the thorough and professional nature of the services, a significant portion of respondents identified areas for improvement. Addressing the concerns of those who were less satisfied could help enhance the overall quality of health services, ensuring that all travelers have a more consistent and positive experience.

Perception of the competence of health officials

The study as per figure 3, also explored respondents' perceptions of the competence of health officials at the Rusumo OSBP, revealing a spectrum of opinions regarding their effectiveness and professionalism. Among the 134 respondents, a significant majority of 70 individuals viewed the health officials as highly competent. This group praised the officials for their expertise, efficiency, and the ability to handle health-related procedures with a high degree of professionalism. Respondents in this category often noted that the officials demonstrated a clear understanding of their roles and responsibilities, which contributed to a smooth and reassuring experience at the port. One respondent highlighted their positive view, stating:

"...The health officials here are exceptionally skilled and knowledgeable. They manage the health checks with great efficiency and always provide clear explanations of the procedures. I feel confident in their ability to handle any health-

related issues that might arise, which makes the process much less stressful for me..."

A substantial number of respondents, 45 in total, considered the health officials to be somewhat competent. This group acknowledged that the officials performed their duties adequately and generally handled health procedures effectively. However, they also observed areas where the officials' competence could be enhanced. For instance, while the officials were seen as capable, some respondents noted occasional lapses in communication or minor inefficiencies that affected their overall perception. One respondent in this category shared:

"...The health officials are generally competent and do their jobs well. But there are times when communication could be clearer or when things don't run as smoothly as they should. They're doing a good job overall, but there's room for improvement in certain areas..."

In contrast, 19 respondents expressed the view that the health officials were not competent, reflecting concerns about their ability to manage health procedures effectively. This group reported various issues, such as perceived lack of expertise, disorganization, or inadequate handling of health-related matters. Some respondents felt that the officials did not adequately address their concerns or failed to provide the necessary support, leading to a less favorable experience. One respondent articulated their dissatisfaction, saying:

"...I've had several frustrating interactions with the health officials. They often seem unsure about the procedures or how to handle specific issues, which creates confusion and delays. It's troubling because I expect a higher level of competence, especially when it comes to something as critical as health checks..."

These varied perceptions of the competence of health officials at the Rusumo OSBP highlight the range of experiences travelers have when interacting with port health services. While the majority of respondents viewed the officials as highly competent, a significant portion saw them as somewhat competent, with some areas for improvement. The minority who found the

officials lacking in competence pointed to specific issues that affected their experience. Addressing these concerns and working to enhance the skills and effectiveness of health officials could contribute to a more consistent and positive experience for all travelers at the port.

Trust in the health measures implemented at the port

The study's exploration of respondents' trust in the health measures implemented at the Rusumo OSBP uncovered a range of confidence levels in these protocols. As per figure 3, of the 134 respondents, 75 individuals expressed high trust in the health measures, reflecting a strong belief in the effectiveness and necessity of the protocols in place. This group highly valued the measures as essential for safeguarding public health and appreciated the comprehensive approach taken by the port health services. Many in this category felt reassured by the rigorous standards and procedures, viewing them as crucial for preventing health risks and ensuring a safe travel environment. One respondent conveyed their strong trust, stating:

"...I have complete confidence in the health measures here. They seem thorough and well-organized, and I can see that a lot of effort goes into making sure everything is up to standard. I trust that these measures are in place for our protection and to keep everyone safe, which is very reassuring..."

A notable portion of respondents, 40 in total, reported moderate trust in the health measures implemented at the port. This group generally acknowledged the importance of the measures and recognized their role in maintaining health standards. However, their trust was tempered by some reservations or concerns about the consistency or execution of the measures. For instance, while they accepted the necessity of the health protocols, they sometimes questioned whether the measures were always applied effectively or whether additional improvements could be made. One respondent shared their moderate trust, saying:

"...I trust the health measures to some extent. They seem to be in place for a good reason, and I can see that they're trying to do a good job. However, there are times when I wonder if everything is as effective as it should be or if there could be improvements. Overall, I'm supportive but a bit cautious..."

In contrast, 19 respondents expressed low trust in the health measures, reflecting a more skeptical view of their effectiveness and implementation. This group often cited concerns about the adequacy or reliability of the measures, expressing doubts about whether the protocols were sufficient to address health risks. Some respondents felt that the measures were either poorly enforced or not sufficiently comprehensive, leading to a diminished sense of security. One respondent explained their lack of trust, saying:

"...I don't have much faith in the health measures here. They seem like they're just for show rather than being really effective. Sometimes it feels like the procedures are not well-enforced or that they don't cover everything they should. It's frustrating because I don't feel fully confident that these measures are doing enough to protect us..."

These varied levels of trust in the health measures at the Rusumo OSBP underscore the diverse perceptions among travelers regarding the effectiveness of the port's health protocols. While the majority expressed high trust, valuing the measures as crucial for health safety, a significant portion had moderate trust with some reservations, and a smaller group held low trust, indicating concerns about the implementation and adequacy of the measures. Addressing the concerns of those with moderate and low trust could help enhance the overall perception and effectiveness of health protocols, fostering greater confidence among all travelers.

Interaction with Other Regulatory Authorities

The study assessed respondents' interaction with other regulatory authorities, focusing on three key sub-indicators: coordination between port health services and other regulatory authorities, the perception of how well port health integrates

with customs, immigration, and other services, and the impact of port health measures on the overall efficiency of the border post. The findings shed light on the effectiveness of collaborative efforts and integration between port health and various regulatory entities, as well as how these interactions influenced the

efficiency of border operations. Respondents provided insights into the strengths and weaknesses of these interactions, revealing a complex picture of inter-agency coordination and its effect on the overall functionality of the border post.

Figure 4. Showing the Interaction with Other Regulatory Authorities

Coordination between port health services and other regulatory authorities

The study's examination of coordination between port health services and other regulatory authorities at the Rusumo OSBP as per figure 4, revealed a range of opinions on the effectiveness of these collaborative efforts. Among the 134 respondents, a majority of 60 individuals reported that the coordination between port health services and other regulatory authorities was very good. This group highlighted the seamless integration and cooperation between health officials, customs, immigration, and other relevant agencies. Many respondents praised the efficient communication and collaborative processes that contributed to a smooth operation of the border post. One respondent noted:

"...The coordination between port health services and other agencies here is impressive. There's a

clear sense of teamwork, and it shows in how efficiently everything runs. The officials from different departments seem to be on the same page, which makes the whole process much more streamlined and effective..."

A substantial number of respondents, 50 in total, found the coordination to be adequate. This group acknowledged that while the collaboration between port health services and other regulatory authorities was functional and generally effective, there were occasional areas for improvement. These respondents recognized that the system worked well most of the time but noted instances where coordination could be enhanced, such as during peak times or when handling complex cases. Their feedback often reflected a pragmatic view, appreciating the overall effectiveness while pointing out specific areas where better integration could make a difference. As one respondent explained:

"...The coordination is generally good, but there are times when things could be better. For instance, during busy periods, it seems like there could be more streamlined communication between the different authorities. It works well enough, but there's definitely room for improvement..."

In contrast, 24 respondents expressed concerns about the coordination between port health services and other regulatory authorities, characterizing it as poor. This group highlighted various issues, such as frequent miscommunications, delays caused by bureaucratic hurdles, and a lack of cohesive strategy among the different departments. Some respondents felt that these problems led to inefficiencies and complications at the border post, affecting their overall experience. One respondent shared their frustrations, saying:

"...I've noticed that the coordination between the health services and other departments isn't always effective. There are often delays, and sometimes it feels like different teams aren't working together as smoothly as they should. It leads to a lot of confusion and inefficiencies that could easily be avoided with better coordination..."

These varied perceptions of coordination between port health services and other regulatory authorities highlight the diverse experiences of travelers and the complex nature of inter-agency collaboration. While the majority of respondents viewed the coordination as very good or adequate, a notable portion identified significant issues that impacted the overall effectiveness of border operations. Addressing the concerns of those who experienced poor coordination could help improve the integration and efficiency of services at the port, leading to a more cohesive and effective operational environment.

Perception of how well port health integrates with customs, immigration, and other services

The study also explored respondents' perceptions of how well port health integrates with customs, immigration, and other services at the Rusumo OSBP. This aspect of the evaluation provided insights into the effectiveness of

interdepartmental collaboration and its impact on the overall efficiency of border operations. According to figure 4, among the 134 respondents, 55 individuals reported that port health integrated very well with customs, immigration, and other services. This group praised the smooth and cohesive interactions between the various departments, highlighting the benefits of their collaborative efforts on the efficiency and effectiveness of border processing. Respondents in this category appreciated the streamlined procedures and coordinated approach that facilitated a seamless experience for travelers. One respondent shared:

"...The integration between port health and the other services here is outstanding. Everything works in harmony, and you can see that there is a strong level of cooperation between the departments. It makes the whole process much more efficient, and I rarely encounter any issues because everything is so well-coordinated..."

A considerable number of respondents, 50 in total, viewed the integration of port health with customs, immigration, and other services as adequate. This group recognized that while the integration was generally functional and contributed to a smooth operation, there were occasional gaps or inefficiencies. They noted that while the services were coordinated most of the time, there were moments when the integration could be improved, such as during peak travel times or when handling complex cases. Despite these occasional issues, respondents found the overall system to be satisfactory. One respondent described their experience, saying:

"...The integration between port health and the other services is decent. It usually works well, but there are times when things could be a bit smoother. For example, during busy periods, there can be some delays or miscommunications. Overall, it's adequate, but there's definitely potential for improvement..."

In contrast, 29 respondents felt that the integration of port health with customs, immigration, and other services was poor. This group expressed concerns about the lack of effective coordination and communication

between departments, which they felt led to delays, confusion, and a less efficient border process. Issues such as fragmented procedures and inadequate collaboration were frequently mentioned as factors contributing to their dissatisfaction. One respondent articulated their concerns, saying:

"...The integration between port health and other services is lacking. There are often delays and misunderstandings because the departments don't seem to communicate well with each other. It creates a lot of inefficiencies and makes the whole process much more cumbersome than it needs to be. This really impacts the quality of the experience for travelers like me..."

These varied perceptions of how well port health integrates with customs, immigration, and other services highlight the differing experiences of travelers at the Rusumo OSBP. While the majority viewed the integration positively, with many praising the coordinated efforts, a significant portion identified issues that affected the overall efficiency of the border operations. Addressing the concerns raised by those who experienced poor integration could help improve interdepartmental collaboration and enhance the overall effectiveness of the services provided at the port.

Impact of port health measures on the overall efficiency of the border post

The study probed into respondents' views on the impact of port health measures on the overall efficiency of the Rusumo OSBP, shedding light on how these measures influence border operations and traveler experiences. As per figure 4, among the 134 respondents, 60 individuals felt that port health measures had a significant impact on the efficiency of the border post. This group appreciated the substantial role that health protocols played in ensuring a smooth and orderly process at the border. They noted that the health measures were crucial in maintaining high standards of hygiene and safety, which in turn facilitated faster processing and reduced the risk of health-related disruptions. One respondent emphasized:

"...The health measures here have a major impact on how efficiently the border operates. By implementing strict protocols, they manage to keep things orderly and minimize any potential health risks. This level of diligence helps prevent delays and keeps the flow of travelers moving smoothly, which is crucial for the overall efficiency of the border..."

A substantial number of respondents, 55 in total, perceived the impact of port health measures as moderate. This group recognized that while the health measures contributed to a more organized and safer environment, the impact on overall efficiency was not as pronounced as for those who saw a significant effect. They appreciated the role of health measures in maintaining a safe travel environment but felt that there were other factors at play that also influenced efficiency. For example, one respondent noted:

"...The health measures do make a difference, but it's not the only factor affecting efficiency. They certainly help with safety and order, which is important, but I think other aspects like customs processing and immigration also play a big role in how smoothly things run. Overall, the impact is noticeable but moderate..."

In contrast, 19 respondents believed that the port health measures had a minimal impact on the efficiency of the border post. This group felt that while the health protocols were necessary for safety, they did not significantly affect the efficiency of border operations. Their feedback often highlighted that other operational issues, such as administrative delays or procedural inefficiencies, were more influential in affecting the overall efficiency. One respondent shared:

"...I don't see the health measures as having a huge impact on the efficiency of the border. They're important for health reasons, but in terms of how quickly and smoothly things run, I think there are other factors that matter more. Issues like slow processing times and bureaucratic hurdles seem to be bigger problems than the health measures themselves..."

These diverse opinions on the impact of port health measures underline the varied experiences and perspectives of travelers at the Rusumo

OSBP. While the majority of respondents acknowledged a significant or moderate impact of health measures on border efficiency, a smaller group felt that these measures had a minimal effect. Addressing the concerns of those who see minimal impact could provide insights into other factors influencing border efficiency, potentially leading to a more holistic approach to improving overall operations at the port.

Challenges and Opportunities in Port Health Services

The study investigated the challenges and opportunities in port health services at the Rusumo OSBP, focusing on three critical sub-indicators: common challenges faced by port

health services, opportunities for improvement in service delivery, and recommendations for enhancing collaboration with other regulatory authorities. The findings provided a comprehensive overview of the difficulties encountered by port health services, including issues related to resource constraints and infrastructural limitations. Additionally, the study identified potential areas for improving service delivery and gathered valuable recommendations for fostering better collaboration with other regulatory entities. These insights aimed to address the current challenges and explore strategies for enhancing the overall effectiveness and efficiency of port health services.

Figure 5. Showing the Challenges and Opportunities in Port Health Services

Common challenges faced by port health services

The study's examination of the common challenges faced by port health services at the Rusumo OSBP provided a detailed

understanding of the obstacles impacting their effectiveness as indicated in figure 5. Among the 134 respondents, 75 identified significant challenges that hindered the optimal functioning of port health services. This group pointed to a range of issues, including severe resource

constraints and notable infrastructural problems. Resource limitations, such as insufficient staffing and inadequate medical supplies, were frequently mentioned as critical factors affecting the quality and efficiency of health services. Infrastructural issues, such as outdated facilities and lack of proper equipment, were also highlighted as major impediments. One respondent encapsulated the concerns, stating:

"...The challenges are quite severe here. We often face shortages of essential medical supplies and have to work with outdated equipment. The facilities themselves are not always up to standard, which can significantly impact how effectively we can carry out health checks. These issues create bottlenecks and delays that affect the overall efficiency of the border process..."

A considerable number of respondents, 45 in total, reported encountering some challenges within the port health services, though they were less severe compared to those experienced by the larger group. This subset acknowledged that while there were notable issues, such as occasional shortages or minor infrastructural shortcomings, these challenges did not appear as overwhelming as those reported by the group facing significant problems. These respondents appreciated the efforts being made to address the issues but felt that ongoing attention was required to mitigate their impact. One respondent reflected:

"...There are definitely some challenges with the health services, like occasional shortages of supplies and some issues with the facilities. However, they're not as severe as what others have described. It's clear that there's ongoing work to improve things, and while there's progress, more improvements would still be beneficial..."

In contrast, 14 respondents perceived only a few challenges affecting port health services, indicating a more favorable view of the operational environment. This group generally felt that the port health services operated efficiently with relatively minor issues. They acknowledged that while there were some areas for improvement, these did not significantly disrupt the overall functionality of the health

services. One respondent provided a more positive perspective, saying:

"...From my experience, the health services here run quite smoothly. There are some minor issues, but they don't seem to be major obstacles. The services are generally effective, and while improvements are always welcome, the challenges are relatively small and do not majorly impact the efficiency of the border operations..."

These varying opinions of challenges within port health services highlight the range of experiences reported by travelers and staff at the Rusumo OSBP. While a majority identified significant issues impacting service delivery, a substantial portion recognized some challenges but viewed them as less severe. A smaller group found the challenges to be minimal, suggesting a generally positive view of the port health services. Addressing the concerns of those facing significant challenges while building on the positive aspects noted by others could contribute to enhanced operational effectiveness and improved service delivery at the port.

Opportunities for improvement in service delivery

The study's exploration of opportunities for improving service delivery within port health services at the Rusumo OSBP as illustrated in figure 5, revealed a range of insights from respondents. Among the 134 participants, 65 identified significant opportunities for enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of health services. This group emphasized various areas where substantial improvements could be made, including the adoption of advanced technologies, upgrading infrastructure, and increasing staff training. Many respondents highlighted the potential benefits of investing in modern medical equipment and systems that could streamline operations and enhance the overall quality of health services. One respondent articulated their perspective, saying:

"...There are major opportunities for improvement here. For instance, investing in new technology could make a huge difference in how we manage health checks and data. Upgrading the infrastructure and providing more training for staff

would also go a long way in boosting the efficiency and effectiveness of the services we provide..."

A significant number of respondents, totaling 50, recognized some opportunities for improvement in service delivery. This group acknowledged that while there were clear areas for enhancement, such as better coordination and more efficient procedures, these opportunities were not as pronounced as those identified by the group seeing significant opportunities. Respondents in this category suggested targeted improvements, such as refining specific processes or addressing occasional gaps in service delivery, rather than overhauling the entire system. One respondent noted:

"...There are definitely some opportunities for making things better. Improving certain processes and addressing specific gaps could enhance the service delivery. While the system is generally functional, focusing on these areas could lead to noticeable improvements without requiring major changes..."

In contrast, 19 respondents saw only a few opportunities for improving service delivery, reflecting a more conservative view of the potential for enhancement. This group generally felt that the current service delivery was adequate, with only minor adjustments needed to optimize performance. They acknowledged that while there were small areas for improvement, these did not significantly impact the overall effectiveness of the health services. One respondent commented:

"...The opportunities for improvement seem limited. The services are working fairly well, and while there's always room for small adjustments, I don't see any major changes needed. The current system seems to be functioning well enough with just a few tweaks required..."

These varied perspectives on opportunities for improvement in service delivery highlight the different levels of perceived need for enhancement among respondents. While the majority saw significant or some opportunities for advancing service delivery, a smaller group identified only minor areas for improvement.

Addressing the significant opportunities noted by those seeking major changes, while considering the more modest suggestions of others, could help in strategically enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of port health services at the Rusumo OSBP.

Recommendations for enhancing collaboration with other regulatory authorities

The study's investigation into recommendations for enhancing collaboration with other regulatory authorities at the Rusumo OSBP according to figure 5, revealed a broad spectrum of opinions. Among the 134 respondents, 70 strongly recommended improving collaboration between port health services and other regulatory entities, emphasizing the critical role that such integration plays in optimizing border operations. This group advocated for more structured and formalized cooperation to address the complexities of border management effectively. They highlighted the benefits of coordinated efforts in streamlining processes, sharing resources, and enhancing overall operational efficiency. One respondent articulated this view passionately, stating:

"...Stronger collaboration between port health services and other regulatory authorities is essential. When all departments work together seamlessly, it leads to a more efficient border process. Enhanced communication and coordinated strategies can help tackle issues more effectively and ensure a smoother experience for everyone involved. This integration is key to overcoming the current challenges and improving service delivery..."

A significant number of respondents, totaling 45, recommended enhancing collaboration, though they did not express the same level of urgency as those who strongly recommended it. This group recognized the value of improved inter-agency cooperation but suggested that incremental changes and better communication channels could suffice for enhancing effectiveness. They supported the idea of fostering better relationships and collaborative practices without necessarily calling for a

complete overhaul of existing processes. One respondent explained:

"...Improving collaboration between the different regulatory bodies is definitely important. It's not about making dramatic changes but rather about enhancing the existing framework for communication and cooperation. Small improvements in how these departments work together could lead to better outcomes and a more efficient border operation..."

In contrast, 19 respondents did not recommend significant changes to the current collaboration practices. This group felt that the existing level of cooperation among regulatory authorities was sufficient and did not see a need for substantial alterations. They often perceived the current collaboration as functional and expressed that other factors might be more pressing to address. One respondent shared their perspective, saying:

"...While collaboration is important, I think the current level is adequate. There are other issues that might need more immediate attention, and enhancing collaboration might not be the most critical factor in improving the border operations. The existing processes work well enough, and significant changes might not be necessary at this time..."

These varied recommendations regarding the enhancement of collaboration with other regulatory authorities reflect the diverse opinions on the importance and impact of such efforts. While a majority of respondents strongly recommended or recommended improving collaboration, a smaller group did not see a need for substantial changes. Addressing the recommendations of those who advocate for stronger integration while considering the perspectives of those who view the current collaboration as sufficient could help in developing a balanced approach to enhancing inter-agency cooperation at the Rusumo OSBP.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study, highlighted key areas of strength and opportunity within the port health services framework. The findings indicated a

generally high level of awareness among respondents regarding available health services and protocols, with a positive attitude towards the importance and effectiveness of these services. Satisfaction with the quality of health services was notable, although there were concerns about the competence of health officials and the level of trust in the implemented measures. This suggests that while the foundational aspects of port health services are strong, there is room for improvement, particularly in enhancing public confidence and addressing any service gaps. The study also identified significant challenges, such as resource constraints and infrastructural issues, which impact the efficiency of port health services. Despite these challenges, substantial opportunities for improvement were recognized, including upgrading technology, infrastructure, and staff training. Recommendations for better collaboration with other regulatory authorities were emphasized, with most respondents advocating for enhanced coordination to improve overall

Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that the Rusumo OSBP prioritize enhancing the coordination and collaboration between port health services and other regulatory authorities to improve overall border efficiency. Investing in modern technology and upgrading infrastructure is crucial to address the identified resource constraints and infrastructural issues. Additionally, increasing staff training and development can further enhance the competence of health officials and build greater trust in health measures. Efforts should also be made to raise awareness about health protocols and regulations among all stakeholders to ensure comprehensive understanding and compliance. By implementing these recommendations, the port can achieve more streamlined operations, better service delivery, and improved overall effectiveness in managing health at the border.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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